

Malate Complex of Yttrium (III)

NIRADA KUMARI MOHANTY and R. K. PATNAIK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-8, Orissa

Manuscript received 9 October 1975; accepted 28 January 1976

Malic acid forms a neutral complex (c) with yttrium below pH 4.0, which dissociates like a dibasic acid at higher pH. The equilibrium constant of the reactions $Y^{3+} + H_2ML \rightleftharpoons C + 3H^+$, $C \rightleftharpoons C^{-1} + H^+$ and $C_1^{-} \rightleftharpoons C_2^{-} + H^+$ are found to be 2.05×10^{-8} , 1.95×10^{-6} and 4.07×10^{-9} respectively.

ROULET *et al.*¹ have reported the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes of malic, maleic and methyl succinic acids with the rare earths. where

This paper deals with the studies on the malate complexes of yttrium in the pH range of 3.0 to 8.4 by pH titration method.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B.D.H. Analar or G.R. Emerek grade. pH, titrations were carried out at $31 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1M by the addition of potassium nitrate. pH measurements were carried out by a Marconi pH meter.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between yttrium and malic acid (Fig. 1) can be represented as

$$K = \frac{[C][H^+]^n}{[Y^{3+}][H_2ML]} \quad \dots (2)$$

It can be shown as in the case of citrate complexes of cadmium², nickel³ and yttrium⁴ and tartrate complex of yttrium⁵ that

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[TML]}{[C]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots (3)$$

When the formation of the complex is complete, $[C] = [Y(NO_3)_3]$. Hence

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[TML]}{[Y(NO_3)_3]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots (3-1)$$

$$\Delta[NaOH] = [NaOH]_B - [NaOH]_A$$

$$\Delta[TML] = [TML]_B - [TML]_A$$

$$a = \frac{k_1}{[H^+]} + \frac{2k_1 \cdot k_2}{[H^+]^2}$$

$$b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2}{[H^+]^2}$$

The dissociation constants, k_1 and k_2 are 5.5×10^{-4} and 2.1×10^{-5} respectively. $[NaOH]_A$, $[NaOH]_B$, $[TML]_A$, $[TML]_B$, $[C]$ and n are represented as molar concentrations of sodium hydroxide at curve A

Fig. 1. pH titration of 100 ml. of solution containing 0.000625 g.mole of malic acid and 0.01 g.mole of potassium nitrate (curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 0.0005 g.mole of yttrium nitrate (curve B) against 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

and B, total malate concentrations at curve A and B, yttrium tartrate complex and the number of protons liberated per gram atom of yttrium respectively.

The number of protons liberated (n) are found to be more than 3 and 4 above pH 4.0 and 7.4 respectively. Below pH 4.0 a neutral complex is formed with the liberation of three protons and the equilibrium constant is calculated as before and recorded in the Table 1. The mean value of K is found to be 2.05×10^{-8} .

In the pH range of 4.0 to 6.6, the neutral complex C dissociates to C_1^- and a proton.

$$\frac{[C_1^-][H^+]}{[C]} = K_1$$

It can be shown as before that

$$\frac{(n-3)[H^+]}{(4-n)} = K_1.$$

The equilibrium constant of the reaction (K_1) were calculated as in the cadmium citrate complex (Table 1). The mean value of K_1 is 1.95×10^{-6} .

Fig. 2. pH titration of 100 ml. of a solution containing 0.0025 g.mole of sodium malate and 0.01 g.mole of potassium nitrate (curve A) and that of same volume of another solution containing the same quantity of the above constituents and 0.0005 g.mole of yttrium nitrate (curve B) against 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

TABLE I. DETERMINATION OF K , K_1 AND K_2 VALUES FROM EXPERIMENT I

pH	$\Delta[NaOH] \times 10^4$	$-\Delta[TML] \times 10^5$	$[M] \times 10^4$	n	$[C] \times 10^4$	$[M^{++}] \times 10^4$	$[H_2ML] \times 10^3$	$K \times 10^8$	$K_1 \times 10^6$	$K_2 \times 10^9$
3.0	26.61	33.0	24.04	1.542	10.57	13.47	6.823	1.549	—	—
3.4	32.41	40.0	23.32	2.118	14.68	8.64	4.036	2.657	—	—
3.6	35.2	43.0	23.01	2.428	17.15	5.86	2.818	1.646	—	—
3.8	39.67	48.0	22.73	2.831	20.9	1.83	1.729	2.343	—	—
5.4	28.55	35.0	21.89	3.435	—	—	—	—	3.066	—
5.6	28.4	34.0	21.81	3.489	—	—	—	—	2.404	—
6.0	27.9	34.0	21.7	3.546	—	—	—	—	1.202	—
6.2	29.4	37.0	21.62	3.668	—	—	—	—	1.27	—
6.6	32.1	40.0	21.51	3.85	—	—	—	—	1.855	—
7.4	37.8	46.0	21.27	4.206	—	—	—	—	—	6.473
8.0	39.0	48.0	21.18	4.292	—	—	—	—	—	4.125
8.2	39.6	50.0	21.14	4.346	—	—	—	—	—	3.338
8.4	40.3	49.0	21.11	4.373	—	—	—	—	—	2.368

Above pH 7.4, the complex C_1^- dissociates to C_2^{--} and a proton according to the reaction

$$K_2 = \frac{[C_2^{--}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]}$$

It can be shown as before that

$$K_2 = \frac{(n-4)[H^+]}{(5-n)}$$

The equilibrium constant (K_2) of the reaction is calculated as before, and recorded in Table 1. The mean value of K_2 is found to be 4.07×10^{-9} .

In the Figure 2, the ratio of metal to ligand is 1 : 5 and hence the formation of complex is assumed to be complete. It is observed from the Table 1 that above pH 7.4 the complex C_1^- dissociates to C_2^{--} and H^+ . Hence above this pH in this experiment it can be shown as in case of manganese⁶ and yttrium⁵ tartrate complexes that

$$[TML] - [Y(NO_3)_3] = p[HML^-] \quad \dots (6)$$

where

$$p = 1 + \frac{k_2}{[H^+]} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1}$$

$$\text{Proton liberated} = 2[C_1^-] + 3[C_2^{--}]$$

$$\text{Acid neutralised} = [NaOH] + r[HML^-]$$

where

$$r = 1 + 2 \frac{[H^+]}{k_1}$$

Hence,

$$2[C_1^-] + 3[C_2^{--}] = [H^+] + [NaOH] + \frac{r}{p} ([TML] - [Y(NO_3)_3])$$

or

$$[C_2^{--}] = [H^+] + [NaOH] + \frac{r}{p} ([TML] - [Y(NO_3)_3]) - 2[Y(NO_3)_3] \quad \dots (7)$$

$$[C_1^-] = [Y(NO_3)_3] - [C_2^{--}] \quad \dots (8)$$

K_2 values were calculated as before and recorded in the Table 2. The mean value of K_2 is 4.79×10^{-9} , which agrees very well with those obtained in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the B.S.I.R. (Orissa) for financial assistance and to the Ministry of Educa-

TABLE 2. DETERMINATION OF K_2 VALUES FROM EXPERIMENT 2

pH	[TML] $\times 10^3$	[NaOH] $\times 10^4$	[M] $\times 10^4$	[C ₂ ⁻⁻] $\times 10^4$	[C ₁] $\times 10^4$	$K_2 \times 10^9$
7.9	11.85	51.23	23.71	3.81	19.90	2.41
8.0	11.79	56.61	23.59	9.43	14.16	6.681
8.1	11.79	56.61	23.59	9.43	14.16	5.29

tion, Government of India for the award of a research fellowship to one of them (N.K.M.)

References

1. R. ROUET, J. FEUZ and T. VUDUC, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1970, 53, 1876.
2. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 673.
3. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 619.
4. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Acta. Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1973, 79, 279.
5. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear, Chem.*, 1973, 35, 1050.
6. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 511.